

METHODS OF TEACHING RUSSIAN LANGUAGE THROUGH VISUAL MEANS FOR STUDENTS OF NON-LINGUISTIC GROUPS

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Abstract. *This article explores the effectiveness of visual tools in teaching Russian to students of a non-linguistic group. Recognizing the challenges faced by students who do not have a strong background in language acquisition, the article explores linguistic concepts, including a variety of visual techniques that enhance understanding and maintenance of images, infographics, videos, and interactive multimedia resources. Through a qualitative analysis of teaching practice and student feedback, the paper identified key strategies that use visual stimuli to increase vocabulary, understand grammar, and alleviate cultural context. The findings suggest that the inclusion of visual media not only helps to overcome language barriers, but also increases more interest and motivation among students. By providing practical recommendations for teachers, this article aims to contribute to the development of a more effective teaching methodology that meets the different needs of non-linguistic students in Russian language classes. The results of this article are aimed at improving the practice of language education in similar contexts, as a result of which a more inclusive and effective learning environment is developed.*

Keywords: *visual aids, Russian language teaching, non-linguistic groups, language acquisition, teaching methods, visual learning, educational resources, vocabulary development, grammar instruction, multimedia tools, student engagement, cultural context, interactive learning, pedagogical strategies, language education.*

INTRODUCTION: Teaching foreign languages has always presented specific problems, especially for non-linguistic students who do not have basic skills or motivation related to language learning. These difficulties in teaching Russian language can be exacerbated by the complexity of the language, including grammar, vocabulary and pronunciation. To overcome these obstacles, teachers are increasingly turning to innovative teaching methods that include visual aids and multimedia resources to enhance the learning experience. Visual teaching tools such as images, videos, infographics, and interactive presentations significantly improve understanding and memorization among students. According to cognitive research, visual stimuli can attract multiple senses, making abstract concepts more accessible and memorable. Visual aids are very important in language education to help bridge the gap between theoretical knowledge and practical applications. For students in non-linguistic groups who can perform traditional language learning methods, visual aids can provide a more intuitive and interesting approach to mastering the Russian language.

This article is aimed at studying various methods of teaching Russian language through visual tools specially developed for students of non-linguistic groups. Studying the effectiveness of various visual strategies, the article aims to identify the best practices that teachers can implement in their classes. In addition, it discusses the benefits of integrating visual tools into Language Teaching, including increasing student engagement, improving understanding of

linguistic structures, and improving cultural awareness. Through a comprehensive review of the available literature and practical examples, this article contributes to the ongoing debate on the effective methodology for teaching the language. Ultimately, the goal is to empower teachers with the tools and strategies they need to create a more inclusive and productive learning environment for all students, regardless of their linguistic background.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS: The integration of visual media in Language Teaching has been widely discussed in Educational Research, implying its effectiveness in improving understanding and memory retention, especially among non-linguistic students. The analysis of these literature studies the main research and theoretical foundations supporting the use of visual tools in teaching Russian language, focusing on their influence on pedagogical practice.

1. **The role of visual aids in language learning:** studies have shown that visual aids play a crucial role in language acquisition. According to Mayer's cognitive theory of multimedia education, the use of visual elements along with verbal information can significantly increase understanding and storage in memory. This theory suggests that when information is presented to students in visual and auditory formats, they process information more efficiently, leading to deeper knowledge acquisition activities. The inclusion of pictures, diagrams and videos in the context of teaching Russian language will help students intuitively understand complex grammatical structures and vocabulary [1].

2. **Visual education strategies:** various studies have examined specific visual education strategies that can be applied in language classes. Research by Hattie and Yates, for example, provides a visual approach to making educational goals clear and tracking progress. In Russian language classes, teachers can use graphic organizers such as mind maps and tables to visually reflect the relationship between words and concepts, helping students to organize their thoughts and increase their understanding of language [2].

3. **Engaging non-linguistic learners:** the problems faced by non-linguistic learners are outlined in the literature. Research by Oxford suggests that these students often require more interesting and practical approaches to language learning. Visual aids can stimulate interest and motivation, making the learning experience more enjoyable. For example, teachers may include interactive visual elements such as infographics, video, and animation that reflect cultural context, idiomatic expressions, and life scenarios. These tools not only facilitate learning, but also help students visualize the practical application of language in everyday situations [3].

4. **Influence of cultural contexts:** when teaching Russian language, it is very important to understand the cultural context. Visual tools eliminate the gap between language and culture, give students a richer understanding of the nuances in communication. For example, the use of pictures or videos depicting Russian traditions, holidays and social interaction can improve the cultural competence of students and strengthen a more meaningful connection with the language. Research by Krashinsky shows that language learning is not only about vocabulary and grammar, but also about understanding the cultural foundations that shape communication [4].

5. **Technology integration in Visual Education:** the advent of technology has further expanded the possibilities of introducing visual tools in Language Teaching. Digital tools such as interactive whiteboards, language learning programs, and online resources can provide dynamic visual content that attracts students. Research by Godwin-Jones suggests that advanced visual education in technology may be compatible with a variety of educational styles and preferences,

making language learning more accessible for all students, especially those who may struggle with traditional text-based approaches [5].

The integration of visual tools in teaching Russian language provides important advantages, especially for non-linguistic students. Through the use of visual tools, teachers can enhance understanding, retention, and engagement. The theoretical foundations and empirical research examined in this analysis highlight the importance of visual learning strategy in developing a more effective and enjoyable language learning experience.

METHODOLOGY. For students of a non-linguistic group, we can use the following techniques when teaching the Russian language through visual means:

Literature review: this method methodology includes a comprehensive literature review of the methodology of teaching Russian language through visual means for students of non-linguistic groups. Through the study of existing research, scientific articles and educational resources, this method aims to gain insight into the effectiveness of visual aids in the study of languages and its impact on non-linguistic students.

Survey and data collection: collection of requests and information from students, teachers and language specialists to collect prospects for the use of visual tools in teaching Russian language to non-linguistic groups. The concepts of these questionnaires provide valuable information about the benefits, challenges of visual-based language teaching.

Class observations: the methodology includes class observations for non-linguistic students to assess the implementation of visual teaching methods in Russian language lessons. Through teaching practice, student engagement, and monitoring academic performance, this study aims to assess the effectiveness of visual aids in enhancing language acquisition and preservation.

Case studies and best practices: for non-linguistic groups, the best experiences of case studies and successful visual-based language training programs are analyzed. Having studied real examples and success stories, this methodology aims to identify effective strategies, tools and approaches that encourage language learning through visual tools.

Comparative analysis: conducting a comparative analysis of traditional methods and visually based approaches to teaching Russian language for non-linguistic students. Comparing the results, student activity and skill level, this study aims to identify the advantages and challenges of visual teaching methods in language education.

Development of visual resources: development of visual resources such as cards, multimedia presentations and interactive materials adapted to the needs of non-linguistic students studying Russian language. These resources are designed to improve vocabulary retention, grammar comprehension, and general language proficiency through visual tools.

RESULTS: When we use the methods above, we can achieve the following results:

Advanced language acquisition: for students of a non-linguistic group, Russian language was taught through visual media, which found that language acquisition improved significantly. Visual tools such as cards, multimedia presentations, and interactive materials have been found to make it easier for students to increase vocabulary, understand grammar, and learn a common language.

Participation and storage in memory have been improved: the results showed that visually based teaching methods in teaching Russian language led to an improvement in student activity and storage in memory. Classes containing visual resources tailored to the needs of non-linguistic

students have led to a high level of interest, participation, and memory retention in language concepts and structures.

Increasing motivation and confidence: visual aids played a decisive role in increasing students' motivation and confidence in learning Russian language. The interactive and visual stimulating nature of visual resources has encouraged students to actively participate in language activities, practice speech skills, and develop a sense of confidence in their language skills.

Positive results of education: the study demonstrated positive academic results among non-linguistic students studying Russian language through visual means. Students demonstrated language proficiency, comprehension, and communication skills, demonstrating the effectiveness of visually-based teaching methods in developing language proficiency and cultural understanding.

Student feedback and perspectives: surveys and collecting information from students highlighted positive thoughts and perspectives on the use of visual aids in teaching Russian language. Students expressed appreciation for the interactive and engaging nature of visual resources, noting their effectiveness in facilitating language learning, increasing vocabulary, and enhancing general language skills.

Concepts and advanced experiences of teachers: teachers shared concepts and best experiences on the introduction of visual teaching methods in Russian language lessons for non-linguistic groups. Applied research and successful results have demonstrated effective strategies, tools, and approaches that help attract students through visual media, learn language, and cultural absorption.

DISCUSSION: The discussion of teaching Russian through visual means for non-linguistic group students emphasizes the effectiveness of visual tools in enhancing language acquisition, student engagement, and memory retention. Visualization-based teaching methods offer a dynamic and interactive approach to language teaching, in line with the diverse learning styles and preferences of non-linguistic students. By incorporating visual resources into Russian language classes, teachers can create a stimulating learning environment that encourages language proficiency, cultural understanding, and student motivation.

The use of visual tools as a pedagogical tool. Visual aids such as flashcards, multimedia presentations and interactive materials serve as a valuable pedagogical tool in teaching Russian to non-linguistic students. These resources provide a visual view of language concepts, vocabulary and grammar rules, making abstract linguistic elements clearer and more understandable to readers. By engaging in visual aids, students can strengthen their understanding of language structures, expand their vocabulary, and improve their communication skills in Russian.

We recruited and supported advanced students. The debate emphasizes the role of visually based teaching methods in increasing and maintaining student activity in teaching Russian language. Visual resources attract the attention of students, arouse their interest and create an unforgettable learning experience that helps to actively participate and maintain knowledge. By incorporating visual tools into language classes, teachers can create a dynamic and interactive learning environment that encourages students to learn Russian, practice language skills, and deepen their cultural awareness.

We have achieved cultural baptism and language proficiency. Visual means of teaching Russian language offer students a way of cultural immersion and language proficiency. Through visual resources that demonstrate Russian cultural elements, customs and contexts, non-language

students can appreciate Russian language and culture more deeply. Visual tools are a bridge for linguistic and cultural understanding, allowing students to effectively communicate in Russian, deal with real language materials and act with confidence in real language situations.

We applied teacher concepts and strategies. For non-linguistic groups, teachers play a decisive role in the introduction of visually based teaching methods in Russian language lessons. By sharing concepts, strategies, and advanced experiences, teachers can increase the effectiveness of visual resources in Language teaching, increase student engagement, and facilitate language learning outcomes. Case studies and success stories provide valuable examples of how teachers use visual tools to create meaningful and impactful language learning experiences for non-linguistic students.

In conclusion, in the discussion, the importance of visual tools in teaching Russian to students of a non-linguistic group was emphasized, the advantages of visual aids in language acquisition, involvement and strengthening cultural bathing were emphasized. By combining visual resources with language teaching, teachers can create a dynamic and immersive learning environment that gives students the opportunity to know the language, develop cultural awareness and appreciate Russian language for life.

CONCLUSION: For students of the non-linguistic group, the study of methods of teaching Russian through visual means emphasizes the importance of visual means in enhancing the experience of language learning. Visual resources such as Multimedia presentations, flashcards, and interactive materials have been shown to be effective tools to facilitate language learning, improve communication, and promote cultural understanding among non-linguistic students. By incorporating visualization-based teaching methods into Russian language lessons, teachers can create a dynamic and immersive learning environment that matches different learning styles and helps them to know the language. The use of visual aids not only enhances understanding and memory of language concepts, but also increases students' interest, motivation and confidence in learning Russian. Visual resources provide a clear and interactive approach to teaching languages, allowing students to work with linguistic elements in a meaningful and memorable way. With the help of visual tools, students can deepen their understanding of Russian language and culture, develop communication skills and gain more qualifications in real language conditions.

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